

MEDICAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.

Bakhrillaeva Marjona.

Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14059610>

Abstract. Medical tourism is a form of tourism facing a rapid growth worldwide in the last few years. In Uzbekistan, medical tourism has become indispensable portion of travel and tourism sector, allowing millions of visitors to get high quality medical services annually. The main objective of this research note is to investigate medical tourism in Uzbekistan applying data which is derived from UZSTAT represents inbound and outbound medical tourist arrivals.

Introduction. In recent years, tourism has been growing at a rapid pace and contributing to the global economy substantially. According to WTTC, the travel & tourism sector contributed 7.6% to global GDP in 2022; an increase of 22% from 2021 and only 23% below 2019 levels. In 2022, there were 22 million new jobs, representing a 7.9% increase on 2021, and only 11.4% below 2019. Being one of the leading industry, tourism comprises several categories and forms such as cultural tourism, ecotourism, educational tourism, adventure tourism, business tourism and medical tourism as well. Medical tourism brings the largest share of economic benefit from tourism and is becoming increasingly popular on a global scale. "Medical tourism" refers primarily to a new phenomenon of travelers leaving family and friends to seek care abroad, often in less developed countries, along with the organizations that support or offer incentives for such travel (Christie M. Reed). Medical Tourism Association states that about 14 million people travel to other countries in need of medical care every year. Currently, Thailand is in the top of destinations for medical tourism followed by Mexico that mostly receives Canadian and American visitors. United States, which is in the third place welcomes 800 thousand people. One of the fastest growing tourism markets in the world, medical tourism now generates US\$60 billion in business annually worldwide (Jones and Keith, 2006, MacReady, 2007).

Literature review. Medical tourism is among the fastest growing sectors, and many countries are now making legal and practical plans to serve it (Vincent C.S., Heung, Deniz, Kucukusta, Haiyan Song, 2010). Medical travel is not new, but the global nature of the cross-border medical care industry is recent and has developed rapidly. (Corinne Packer, Ronald Labonté, Vivien Runnels, 2010). Medical tourism and health tourism are used synonymously most of the

time, but there are some distinguishing features between those two where health and wellness tourism indicates travel to spa resorts or for traditional and alternative therapies (Sunita Reddy,2010) and medical tourism encompasses primarily and predominantly biomedical procedures, combined with travel and tourism (Whittaker 2008, Connell 2006). Medical tourism is commonly perceived and popularly depicted as an economic issue, with high costs of domestic health care being a major driver of individual demand, and with these expenditures being a major driver on the supply side for countries and companies who feel they can offer significant cost advantages elsewhere to large numbers of potential patients who are willing to vote with their feet (Vivien Runnels a, P.M. Carrera 2012,).

This study analyzes medical tourism inflows and outflows in Uzbekistan. Though Uzbekistan contribution of travel and tourism to GDP (% of GDP) fluctuated substantially in recent years, it tended to decrease through 2000 - 2019 period ending at 3.4 % in 2019. Medical tourism in Uzbekistan can be a convenient option for foreigners who are residing in Central Asia, while quality but inexpensive lab work, diagnostic tests and basic medical procedures can be easily incorporated into tourists' travel itineraries. Those who prefer natural remedies will appreciate Uzbekistan's trained specialists offering acupuncture, homeopathic cures and massage therapy, while all can benefit from the country's recreational options offered as a part of (advantour.com).

Data and Methodology.

Table 1.Number of people who crossed the border of Republic of Uzbekistan for medical purposes (thousand people).

Year	Total	From CIS countries	From other countries
2019	55,5	55,4	0,1
2020	15,0	15,0	0,0

Source: UZSTAT.

Table 2.Number of people who left Republic of Uzbekistan for medical purposes(thousand people).

Year	Total	To CIS countries	To other countries
2019	37,2	29,5	7,7
2020	16,5	9,5	7,0

Source: UZSTAT

As for 2021, data on accommodations of persons in specialized accommodation facilities regarding placement of persons by purpose of travel illustrates 423,9 (thousand people) in medical and wellness procedures.

Furthermore, in 2022 foreign citizens from the total number of trips, the purpose of which was treatment, mainly came from Tajikistan - 8.73 thousand people (47.3%), Kazakhstan - 8.07 thousand people (43.8%) and the Kyrgyz Republic - 1.36 thousand people (7.4%).

CIS countries - Commonwealth of Independent States - Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan.

Results. Results of the findings suggest that a great proportion of tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan for medical purposes are from CIS countries, which some of them are bordered with Uzbekistan. As shown in the table 1, total arrivals to Uzbekistan for medical tourism in 2019 is 55,5, almost entire tourists coming from CIS countries, except 0,1 from other countries.

In 2020, the whole inflows come from CIS countries for treatment purposes.

Outbound tourism flows in 2019 for medical tourism in Uzbekistan points total of 37,2, to CIS countries 29,5, and 7,7 for non-CIS countries. In 2020 the trend drops to 16,5 with 9,5 to CIS countries and 7,0 for other countries. Number of people traveling for medical purposes from Uzbekistan to CIS countries relatively greater than to other countries. In 2020, there were no visitors for medical purposes in Uzbekistan from other countries except CIS countries.

CIS countries play significant role in tourism flows, particularly Tajikistan 8.73 thousand people in 2022. Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan also share significant amount of influx in medical tourism.

Conclusion and Policy implication. Medical tourism in Uzbekistan has become one of the predominant tourist destination in Central Asia. Current paper analyzed medical tourism in Uzbekistan, both inflows and outflows using data from UZSTAT. Findings reveal that major contributors of inbound tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan are CIS countries, such as Tajikistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. This fact ensures the quality of medical services and improvements have reached certain levels in Uzbekistan, but still some challenges remain to reach Uzbek medical tourism top levels on the global scale as the numbers of visitors from another countries are less than CIS countries. Moreover, citizens of Uzbekistan prefer foreign medicine services to domestic treatment at some level

, suggesting medical tourism should be improved in Uzbekistan in terms of understanding patients' needs and expectations.

References:

- 1.WTTC - World travel and tourism council.
- 2.Christie M. Reed ,2008,Medical Tourism
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcna.2008.08.001>
- 3.CorinnePacker,Ronald Labontè, Vivien Runnels ,
Medical Tourism Today: What Is the State of Existing Knowledge
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44660694>
3. Sunita Reddy,2010 ,Medical tourism in India: progress or predicament?
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/27807028>
- 4.VincentC.S.,Heung, Deniz,Kucukusta, HaiyanSong,2010
Medical tourism development in Hong Kong: An assessment of the barriers
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2010.08.012>
- 5.Corinne Packer,Ronald Labonté, VivienRunnels, 2010.
Medical Tourism Today: What Is the State of Existing Knowledge
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44660694>
- 6.Whittaker 2008, Medical migrations
- 7.Connell 2006
- 8.Vivien Runnels a, P.M. Carrera 2012,
advantour.com

